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COVID Pandemic and Research in VIMSAR – A Literature Review

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Veer Surendra Sai Institute of Medical Sciences and Research (VIMSAR), located in Burla, in the district of Sambalpur, is the second oldest medical college in the state of Odisha, India, established in 1969. It has a glorious history in the past catering to the people of the under developed western part of Odisha, Chhattisgarh and Jharkhand. The institute has been actively involved in health research during the COVID-19 pandemic. The following commentary is based upon review of published research finding on PubMed that discusses the research activities undertaken by researchers in VIMSAR during the pandemic. PubMed was selected because it is recognised world-wide for its indexing quality of journal articles and is also recommended by the National Medical Commission.

The search criteria included

("vimsar"[All Fields] OR "vimsar burla"[All Fields] OR "veer surendra sai institute of medical science and research"[All Fields] OR ("VEER"[All Fields] AND "SURENDRA"[All Fields] AND "sai"[All Fields]) AND ("covid"[All Fields] OR "sars cov"[All Fields] OR "coronavirus"[All Fields] OR "pandemic"[All Fields])).

It returned 17 results which were subjected to full text review for further screening. The final results included 10 articles. Most were from the department of Community medicine. Other publications involved researchers from Department of ENT (Oto-laryngology & Head-Neck Surgery), Forensic Medicine and Toxicology, Microbiology, Pharmacology and Paediatrics. Out of these papers five were research initiated in VIMSAR where as the other five were basically multi centric studies involving researchers from VIMSAR.

Now coming to individual articles four of them were based upon the COVID 19 vaccine focusing on the anti-spike immunoglobulin level post vaccination. One study was one of its first in India and supplemented the role of ChAdOx1 vaccine (Adenovirus-vectored vaccine developed by Oxford and Astra-Zeneca) as a potent immunogenic agent with results showing more than 99% of the recipients developing neutralizing antibody after two doses.[1] Another research paper highlighted the waning of antibody post six months after second dose of ChAdOx1 and laid evidence for booster dose in the Indian Population.[2]

Research conducted in the Department of Forensic Medicine and Toxicology demonstrated increased burden of suicide during the pandemic which supplemented the research finding in developed nation. They reported four-fold rise in Suicides during the initial part of COVID pandemic.[3]

The department of Microbiology described the challenges they faced for setting up of a COVID LAB (BSL II) in their department in record time in resource constraint setting.[4] The case report from department of ENT described a cut throat injury during the COVID pandemic.[5] Others were mainly multi centric research involving COVID vaccine, MISC, Rapid antigen Test and Google trends based surveillance.[6]

Overall, VIMSAR has played a crucial role in COVID-19 research and mitigation strategies in the region. The research conducted by VIMSAR has provided valuable insights into the epidemiology and clinical outcomes of COVID-19 in the local population and has contributed to the development of guidelines and protocols for the management of COVID-19 patients. But comparison to other leading institutions VIMSAR is lagging behind somewhat.

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